

THE IMPACT OF DIGITALIZATION OF PUBLIC SERVICES AND ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE ON THE COMPETENCE OF STATE CIVIL APPARATUS TOWARDS INTEGRATED GOVERNANCE

ANWAR SADAT ^{1*}, TJAHJA SUPRIYATNA ², SADU WASISTIONO ³ and SRIYONO JOKO SUTOPO ⁴

¹ Universitas Satyagama, Jakarta, Indonesia, Universitas Muhammadiyah Buton.

^{2,3,4} Universitas Satyagama, Jakarta, Indonesia.

Email: ¹anwarsadat685@gmail.com (*Corresponding Author), ²supriyatna1953@gmail.com, ³sadu_ws@yahoo.com

⁴sriyonojokosutopo@gmail.com

Abstract

It is expected that as public services become more digitalized, government task implementation would improve in efficiency, transparency, and accountability. Meanwhile, a strong corporate culture can generate a work environment that enhances State Civil Service capabilities. This study seeks to analyze the relationship between organizational culture and the elements that drive digital transformation, as well as the capability of the state civil apparatus in the digitalization of public services. The research methodology is based on a positivist quantitative approach. We all need new public-sector efforts in this digital age. One such example is digital public services. Although it is still challenging to implement this revolutionary digital public service, it must be made available immediately for the community's comfort and convenience. The study's findings show that the variable "Digitalization of Public Services" has a favorable and significant impact on the competency level of the State Civil Apparatus. The organizational culture variable has a positive and minor impact on the competency of the state civil apparatus, as indicated by a positive and significant CR (Critical Ratio). Integrated Government has a positive and negligible impact on the competency of state civil apparatus. The integrated government variable may mediate the relationship between organizational culture and public service digitization in terms of state civil apparatus capability.

Keywords: Include Public Services, Digitalization, Competency, Organizational Culture, State Civil Service, And Integrated Governance.

INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation in the public sector has emerged as a top priority for governments worldwide, including Indonesia. The goal of digitalizing public services is to supply them aster, more precisely, and efficiently. However, the success of digitalization is defined not just by the technology, but also by the people who utilize it. On the other side, organizational culture serves as the framework for state civil servants' conduct, attitudes, and performance. An adaptive and innovative organizational culture can motivate state employees to keep learning and adapting to changes in technology and the workplace. As a result, it is critical to understand how these two factors, namely digitization and organizational culture, interact to influence the competency of the state civil service. In an era of globalization and rapid advancement of information technology, digitalization of public services has become a must for governments worldwide. Digitalization not only improves people's access to public services, but it also boosts government efficiency, openness, and accountability. The use of digital technology in

public services reduces cumbersome bureaucracy and speeds up administrative processes, resulting in increased public satisfaction. Along with digitalization efforts, characteristics of organizational culture are vital in improving the competency of state civil servants. A positive, inclusive, and learning-oriented organizational culture can foster a work environment that helps state civil servants develop their capacities and skills.

On the other side, an organizational culture that is inflexible and resistant to change might stymie digitalization attempts while increasing the competence of the state civil service. The quality of community service is inadequate, and the government has not carried out the people's mandate to its full potential.

Government personnel, on the other hand, provide low quality services to the public as a result of the government's incapacity to perform its obligations optimally. Finally, government impedes the progress of both the state and the nation. For example, bureaucratic reform in Indonesia has not gone as planned due to government personnel' lack of competency, which has prevented them from providing real changes in public services, particularly in the areas. Wahyu Saputra Basri and Johannes (n.d.).

The Republic of Indonesia Ombudsman's report on the results of the 2021 Public Service Standards Compliance Assessment indicates that regional compliance with national public service regulations is similarly dismal. According to statistics from 416 district administrations assessed, 87 (20.91%) are in the red zone (low compliance), 226 (54.33%) are in the yellow zone (medium compliance), and just 103 (24.76%) are in the green zone (high compliance). (The Ombudsman, 2021).

The competency of state civil workers is critical to achieving integrated governance. Competent state civil servants can respond promptly and appropriately to a variety of issues that arise throughout the delivery of public services. Integrated government necessitates the employment of state civil servants who are not only technically adept, but also managerially capable and adaptable to technology and social trends.

The purpose of this study is to examine how digitalization of public services and organizational culture affect the competency of state civil servants in the setting of integrated government. This study will use a quantitative method to present a comprehensive picture of the interplay between digitalization, organizational culture, and the competence of state civil servants.

It is envisaged that the outcomes of this research will help to shape policies and strategies for creating state civil servants who are more effective and relevant to the problems of the digital age.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study collects data from respondents using a quantitative methodology, namely a survey method. A quantitative study approach was chosen because it allows for the systematic and objective measurement and analysis of the impact of digitalization of public services and organizational culture on the competence of state civil workers.

The participants in this study are all state civil officials who work in various government departments in Indonesia. Given the huge population, this study used purposive sampling to generate a representative sample. Sample admission criteria include state government officials who are directly involved in public services and have worked for at least a year to demonstrate appropriate familiarity with digitalization and organizational culture.

Research Instrument

Measuring state civil workers' attitudes about the implementation of digital technology in public services. A five-point Likert scale was utilized, with responses ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree."

Measuring state public workers' attitudes toward the organizational culture in which they operate. A five-point Likert scale was employed. Assessing the competence of state public workers in a variety of areas, including technical, management, and adaptive abilities. A five-point Likert scale was employed.

Data Collection Procedures

Data was collected by distributing questionnaires both online and offline. Online surveys were circulated via email and online survey platforms, while offline questionnaires were delivered directly to state public personnel in many government institutions. Before data collection, the questionnaire was evaluated (pilot test) to confirm that it was valid and reliable.

Data Analysis Technique

The acquired data was examined with descriptive and inferential statistical methods. To describe respondents' demographic profiles and the distribution of responses to each questionnaire item.

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) ensures construct validity, whereas Cronbach's Alpha test ensures instrument reliability. Data normality test, model fit test, or goodness of fit. Use the t test to determine the relevance of each independent variable (digitalization and organizational culture) on the dependent variable (competence of state civil servants).

RESULTS

Test Validity or CFA Test (*Confirmatory Factor Analysis*)

The CFA test, also known as a construct validity test, is designed to determine whether each indication can explain current constructs. Indicators with a p value < 0.05 and loading factor > 0.5 were used to measure research variables, while those with a p value > 0.05 and loading factor < 0.5 were removed from the model.

According to Ghozali The first thing to look at is the significance value (P value); if it is greater than 0.05, the indicator is removed from the model; second, look at the standardized value loading factor (Estimate value); if it is less than 0.50, the indicator is removed because it is considered an invalid measure latent construct.

Figure 1: Results of CFA analysis of exogenous variables

Results analysis confirmatory the can explained :

1. Test CFA on Variable Exogenous

Table 1: Maximum Likelihood Estimates Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E	CR	P	Label
X1.6	<---	TdPP	1,000				
X1.5	<---	TdPP	1,006	,330	3,048	,002	par_1
X1.4	<---	TdPP	1,164	,362	3,212	,001	par_2
X1.3	<---	TdPP	1,454	,385	3,782	***	par_3
X1.2	<---	TdPP	,862	,264	3,263	,001	par_4
X1.1	<---	TdPP	1,290	,350	3,684	***	par_5
X2.5	<---	PkO	1,000				
X2.4	<---	PkO	1,176	.116	10,128	***	par_6
X2.3	<---	PkO	1,161	.114	10,159	***	par_7
X2.2	<---	PkO	1,070	.122	8,789	***	par_8
X2.1	<---	PkO	1,147	.115	9,962	***	par_9
Z3	<---	WoG	1,000				
Z2	<---	WoG	,759	,236	3,219	,001	par_10
Z1	<---	WoG	1,080	,277	3,904	***	par_11
Y1	<---	KSDM	1,000				
Y2	<---	KSDM	,954	.101	9,420	***	par_12
Y3	<---	KSDM	1,086	,112	9,703	***	par_13
Y4	<---	KSDM	1,026	,129	7,937	***	par_14
Y5	<---	KSDM	1,074	.121	8,903	***	par_15

The P value (Probability) in the Regression Weight output must be substantial (above 0.05) before the indicator can be eliminated. As you can see, all of the probability values have the *** sign, indicating that they are significant at the 0.001 level and less than 0.05. Based on the Regression Weight, the indicators that comprise the Digitalization of Public Services (DIPb) variable and the Organizational Culture Change variable are declared valid, but significant results do not always provide factor loading (estimate value) that is high. The loading factor (estimate) value in the Standardized Regression Weight is greater than 0.5, indicating that there is a construct to explain. Can It is known that all estimate values exceed 0.5. This demonstrates that these indicators can describe existing constructions.

2. Test CFA on variable Endogenous and Entervening Variables

Figure 2: Results of CFA analysis of Exogenous and Entervening variables

Table 2: Maximum Likelihood Estimates Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E	CR	P	Label
Z3	<---	WoG	1,000				
Z2	<---	WoG	,759	,236	3,219	,001	par_10
Z1	<---	WoG	1,080	,277	3,904	***	par_11
Y1	<---	KSDM	1,000				
Y2	<---	KSDM	,954	.101	9,420	***	par_12
Y3	<---	KSDM	1,086	,112	9,703	***	par_13
Y4	<---	KSDM	1,026	,129	7,937	***	par_14
Y5	<---	KSDM	1,074	.121	8,903	***	par_15

Table 2 shows that the Regression Weight output is based on the P value (Probability); if the value is not significant (more than 0.05), the indicator must be eliminated. As you can see, all of the probability values have the *** sign, indicating that they are significant at the 0.001 level, which is likewise not significant enough from 0.05. This The Regression Weight indicator, which combines the Human Resource Competency Development variable and the Integrated Government variable, has been certified legitimate, but significant results do not

always give high factor loading (Estimate value > 0.5). The loading factor (estimate) value in the Standardized Regression Weight is greater than 0.5, indicating that these indicators can explain existent constructs. Can it is known that all estimate values exceed 0.5. This demonstrates that these indicators can describe existing constructions.

Data Normality Test

Data normality is one of the requirements for SEM to be operational while creating process models. In evaluating normalcy the data in this study were analyzed using the z value. This z value will be seen with the crucial value defined by the level of importance. The determined value is 0.01 with a critical mark of ± 2.58 . When processing data with IBM Amos 22, mark z is noticed from the crucial ratio. The table below shows the results of the test for normalcy.

Table 3: Assessment of normality

Variable	min	max	skew	cr	kurtosis	cr
Y5	1,000	5,000	-1,167	-4,835	,566	1,173
Y4	1,000	5,000	-,764	-3,164	-,161	-,333
Y3	1,000	5,000	-,744	-3,084	-,234	-,485
Y2	1,000	5,000	-,621	-2,574	-1.027	-2.127
Y1	1,000	5,000	-,693	-2,872	-,179	-,370
Z1	1,000	5,000	-,496	-2,055	-,272	-,564
Z2	1,000	5,000	-,617	-2,555	,070	,146
Z3	1,000	5,000	-,912	-3,778	,784	1,625
X2.1	1,000	5,000	-,856	-3,546	,688	1,426
X2.2	1,000	5,000	-,603	-2,500	-,221	-,459
X2.3	1,000	5,000	-,647	-2,682	-,310	-,642
X2.4	1,000	5,000	-,590	-2,443	-,743	-1,538
X2.5	1,000	5,000	-,627	-2,599	-,149	-,308
X1.1	3,000	5,000	-,883	-3,657	-,226	-,468
X1.2	3,000	5,000	-,971	-4,021	-,059	-,122
X1.3	2,000	5,000	-,524	-2,170	,352	,730
X1.4	2,000	5,000	-,466	-1,932	-,112	-,232
X1.5	2,000	5,000	-,697	-2,888	,117	,243
X1.6	1,000	5,000	-,779	-3,226	,028	,059
Multivariate					5,565	1,000

In Table 3, According to the normalcy evaluation output, there is no critical ratio value more than +2.58 or less than -2.58. The highest number for Skewness is -2.127, while the highest value for Kurtosis is 1.625. Based on these findings, we can conclude that the normalcy assumption is met.

Goodness of fit test

The goal of the model fit test or Goodness of fit is to discover out whether the model that is built is fit or not, namely whether the manifest variables (variables indicator) can explain the latent variable. There is.

Figure 3: Full Model Structural Equation Modeling Test Results

The output results can be seen in the AMOS Output file attachment, and the results can be obtained summarized as follows :

Table 4: Results Goodness of Fit

Goodness of Fit	Cut off value	Results	Decision
Probability	≥ 0.05	0, 194	Good Fit
Chi Square	Expected to be small	160,520	Marginal Fit
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.859	Bad Fit
AGFI	≥ 0.90	0.817	Bad Fit
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.935	Good Fit
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.841	Marginal Fit
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.592	Bad Fit
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.0 31	Marginal Fit

(Source: Data primary ones processed, 2024)

Results test Goodness of fit after modification model as following :

Figure 4: Results modification model SEM

The number under the huge mark indicates the minimal chi-square, which will decrease if the associated variables are connected. Connection between variable error this continues until the model is certified fit. Following the addition of error variable correlation, such as that shown in yellow between e 8 and e 19, e 8 with e 15, e 8 with e 12, etc. Finally, the developed model stated that it fits with the data. Overall, a structural model can be regarded fit, and the procedure the next stage is to determine whether or not the independent factors have a substantial influence on the dependent variable. The findings are as follows:

1. Variables for Digitalization of Public Services

Table 5: Results Reliability Variable Digitalization of Public Services

Variable X1	Loading Standard	Error (e)	Value e	Construct Reliability Calculation Results
X1.6	0.818	e6	0.515	0.87
X1.5	0.735	e5	0.471	
X1.4	0.779	e4	0.237	
X1.3	0.692	e3	0.254	
X1.2	0.763	e2	0.183	
X1.1	0.827	e1	1,336	

Table 5 shows that X1.1, X1.2, X1.3, X1.4, X1.5, and which The indicators in the Digitalization of Public Services variable are deemed Reliable, because they have value construct reliability of greater than 0.7, therefore it may be used as a standard indicator. For recommended in supporting the digitalization of public services varied...

2. Organizational Culture Variables

Table 6: Results Reliability Variable Organizational culture

Variable X2	Loading Standard	Error (e)	Value e	Construction reliability calculation results
X2.4	0.751	e10	1.09	0.75
X2.3	0.818	e9	1.11	
X2.2	0.777	e8	0.877	
X2.1	0.794	e7	0.429	

Based on table 6, it is clear that X2.1 and X2.2 are indicators of the Organizational Culture variable that have been deemed reliable. Because their value construct reliability is greater than 0.7, they can be utilized as a standard indicator for supporting the organizational culture variable.

3. State Civil Servant Competency Variables

Table 7: Results Reliability Variable ASN Competency

Variable Y	Loading Standard	Error (e)	Value e	Construct Reliability Calculation Results
Y.5	0.841	e16	1,198	0.709
Y.4	0.83	e15	1,535	
Y.3	0.784	e14	1,258	
Y.2	0.792	e13	1,256	
Y,1	0.765	e12	1,355	

Based on table 7 it can be seen that Y.1, Y.2, Y.3, Y.4, and Y.5 are is an indicator of the state civil servant competency variable which is declared Reable, because it has value construct reliability is more than 0.7 so it can be used as a standard indicator For recommended in supporting the competency variables of state civil servants.

4. Integrated Government Variables

Table 8: Results Reliability Variable Integrated Government

Z variables	Loading Standard	Error (e)	Value e	Construct Reliability Calculation Results
Z.3	0.889	e19	0.822	0.702
Z.2	0.831	e18	0.819	
Z.1	0.87	e17	1,198	

Based on table 8, it can be seen that Z.1, Z.2, and Z.3 are is indicators on the Integrated Government variable declared Reable, because it has value construct reliability is more than 0.7 so it can be used as a standard indicator for recommended in supporting the Integrated Government variable.

DISCUSSION

The Impact of Digitalizing Public Services on the Competence of State Civil Apparatus

According to the test results for the first hypothesis, there is a positive and substantial relationship between the digitization of public services and the competency of state civil servants in regional administrations. The AMOS output shows that the CR value of 2.531 is more than 1.96, and the P value of.011 is greater than alpha 0.05. This finding suggests that the varying digitalization of public services has a favorable and significant impact on the competency of state civil servants. The presence of a positive and significant influence suggests that the deployment of digitalization of public services must be complemented with competent human resource capabilities. Furthermore, changes in the social environment are tied to the characteristics of the contemporary state civil apparatus, specifically the information era, which is based on knowledge and technology that may be used. Currently, the competency of state civil servants in regional governments is more geared toward knowledge workers, which means that human resources must have new knowledge that is matched with the continuing transformation. The state civil apparatus can easily realize the digital transformation of public services by employing competent human resources who are focused, innovative/creative, responsive, communicative, experienced, results-oriented, and trustworthy. internet and other digital technologies for delivering information from the government to the public, business partners, businesses, employees, and other associated institutions online.

Influence of Organizational Culture on the Competency of State Civil Apparatus

According to the test results for the second hypothesis, there is a positive but minor influence of organizational culture on the competency of state civil servants in local governments. According to the questionnaire responses, the corporate culture views their work to be more than just mastering and enjoying their field of work, indicating that these employees are

experienced. The AMOS report shows that the CR value of 2,800 is larger than 1.96, and the P value of .072 is less than alpha 0.05. These findings suggest that organizational culture characteristics have a positive but small effect on the competency of state civil workers. The statistical T value is known based on the findings of the Significance of Mediation (Sobel Test) computation, as shown in Table 4.17. 1.97 is greater than 1.96, and the P value is 0.049, which is smaller than alpha 0.05. These findings suggest that integrated government characteristics modulate the effect of culture on the competence of state civil servants. To decide whether the study hypothesis is accepted or rejected, parameters are employed based on the degree of error tolerance $D = 5\%$ (0.05), with a criteria value of $p = <0.05$ and a critical limit of 1.96. These values are utilized to make decisions on the research hypothesis. Interpretation of the link between each hypothesized variable and its coefficients.

The Impact of Digitalization of Public Services on Integrated Governance

According to the test results of the third hypothesis, the digitalization of public services has a favorable and significant impact on integrated government. The AMOS output has a CR value of 8,018. It is bigger than 1.96 and has a P value of 0.01, which is less than alpha 0.05. As a result, it is argued that the digitization of public services has a good and considerable impact on integrated governance. The results of this third test are consistent with prior research studies conducted by Natalisa, D. (2021). The digital transformation of public services must prioritize the public interest, resulting in increased government investment in technology infrastructure and human resources, as well as the development of an innovation culture in public services.

Furthermore, it is critical to adapt user-centered design ideas and broaden the use of technology in public services to other industries. The government should also encourage community involvement in the development and application of technology in public services. Aside from that, openness, accountability, and non-discrimination in public services are also crucial concepts for developing good public services in the digital age. Furthermore, it indicates the existence of a good and important relationship between the digitalization of public services and organizational culture via integrated government.

The Effect of Digitalization of Public Services on the Competence of State Civil Apparatus through Integrated Government

According to the test results of the fourth hypothesis, there is a positive and substantial relationship between the digitization of public services through integrated government as an intervening variable and the competency of the state civil machinery. The AMOS output presented in Table 4.16 indicates that the CR value is 6.357, which is more than 1.96, and the P value is less than alpha 0.05.

As a result, our findings demonstrate that varied digitalization of public services has a positive and considerable impact on the competence of the state civil service. The statistical T value can be determined using the findings of the Significance of Mediation (Sobel Test) computation, which are shown in Table 4.17. As large as 2.007 is bigger than 1.96, and the P value of 0.044 is less than alpha 0.05. This finding indicates that the integrated government variable mediates

the relationship between the digitalization of public services and the competency of state civil servants.

Future information technology developments can be chosen embraced to fit each government agency's internal and external environment. The AMOS output presented in Table 4.16 indicates that the CR value of 2,079 is larger than 1.96 and the P value is less than alpha 0.05.

These findings suggest that the integrated government variable has a considerable impact on the competency of state civil workers. The positive and considerable influence demonstrates that integrated government must be supported by dependable human resources since running an integrated system combines the components of sub-subsystems into one system and ensures that these sub-systems function as one unified system.

The results of this sixth test are consistent with the findings of previous research tests conducted by Aminah, S., and Saksono, H. (2021), which suggest that the adoption of e-Government thus far has had a favorable influence on public services. This change resulted in the presentation of a number of e-Government apps, including Government to Citizen (G2C), Government to Business (G2B), and Government to Government (G2G).

The Impact of Organizational Culture on the Capability of State Civil Apparatus through Integrated Government

According to the testing results of the fifth hypothesis, there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational culture through integrated governance and the competency of the state civil service. The AMOS output shows that the CR value is 2,079, which is larger than 1.96, and the P value is less than alpha 0.05. This finding demonstrates that the integrated government variable has a considerable effect on the competency of the state civil service.

This refers to theory, which claims that the correlation between variables is an error (unique factors covariance), will always there may be times when a large number of questions are submitted at once, in which case errors in one question item have a positive impact on errors in other items. Added connectivity. This error variable is evaluated constantly until the model is declared fit.

The statistical T value can be determined using the findings of the Significance of Mediation (Sobel Test) computation, which are shown in Table 4.17. 1.97 is greater than 1.96, and the P value is 0.049, which is smaller than alpha 0.05. This finding indicates that, variable integrated governance mediates the influence of organizational culture on the competency of the state civil service.

According to these findings, integrated government becomes mediation because it has the potential to create a new work culture that necessitates adaptation from the state civil apparatus in order to foster innovation and creativity at work, with the state civil apparatus playing the most important role in realizing an integrated and sustainable integrated government.

It is envisaged that state civil servants in government agencies will possess leadership and technical skills, as well as an acceptable degree of integrated government literacy, to ensure that integrated government services are given and utilized maximally.

CONCLUSION

Data analysis and processing methods use SPSS software for *exploratory factor analysis* and AMOS for *confirmatory factor analysis* and AMOS. After testing the primary data, the following conclusions can be drawn.

- 1) The Public Service Digitalization variable has a positive and significant effect on ASN Competency Development. The results of the research that has been carried out show that the CR (*Critical Ratio*) value is positive.
- 2) The Organizational Culture variable has a positive and insignificant effect on ASN Competency. The results of the research that has been carried out show that the CR (*Critical Ratio*) value is positive.
- 3) The Integrated Government variable has a positive and insignificant effect on ASN Competency. The results of the research that has been carried out show that the CR (*Critical Ratio*) value is positive.
- 4) Integrated Government variables can be a mediating influence between the Digitalization of Public Services and the Competence of State Civil Apparatus. The results of the research that has been carried out show that the CR (*Critical Ratio*) value is positive.
- 5) The Integrated Governance variable mediates the influence between Organizational Culture and State Civil Apparatus Competence. The results of the research that has been carried out show that the CR (*Critical Ratio*) value is positive.

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